

The Positive Psychological Capital of Smallholder Farmers and Its Determinants: A Case Study of the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa.

Author Details:

Douglas Kibirige (Ph.D.) - Senior Lecturer at the Department of Agricultural Economics and Management, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Eswatini, Eswatini.

Abstract

Positive psychological capital of a smallholder farmer refers to farmer's intrinsic values like confidence, hope, optimism, and resilience in organizing and carrying out all possible actions required to achieve the desired agricultural performance. This article examined the correlates of farmers' positive psychological capital and farmer/farm characteristics. Based on the literature review and conditions set to achieve an adequate and consistent principal component analysis results, a 12-item rating scale with 4 point rating categories was established to assess the four positive psychological capacities of smallholder farmers. Primary data was collected from 79 smallholder farmers of Cofimvaba and Peddi communities in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. Generally, farmers exhibited higher optimistic and confidence related behavior with low hope and resilience levels. Education, the source of water, access to credit, and household size were identified as farmer/farm characteristics that have a positive and significant impact on farmers' resilience and confidence related behaviors. Government support in the form of farm-input subsidies was found to have a positive and significant impact on both farmers' hope and confidence related behaviors. To reverse the situation of poor, stagnant and declining smallholder agriculture among black people in the Eastern Cape, South African government should consider improving farmers' positive psychological capital through catalyzing policies triggered towards improved access to education, access to water, agricultural credit, labor saving technology, and farm-input subsidies. The findings of this study also have key implications for positive psychological counseling of smallholder farmers.

Keywords: *smallholder farmers, positive psychological capital, hope, optimism, resilience, confidence, factor Analysis, principal component.*

1.1 Introduction

According to Steyn (1982), "human element" is a key factor in agricultural development because of its importance in farm decision making. Success depends on rational decision making, which in turn, depends on the social-physiological characteristics of the farmers (Steyn, 1982). There is an increasing concern about the role of positive psychological capital in enhancing organizational performance globally. Luthans, Luthans, and Luthans (2004) simply defined positive psychological capital as "whom you are" as opposed to "What you are" (human capital) and "whom you know" (social capital). Nevertheless, positive psychological capital has been recognized as a key intangible capital that influences organizational performance and efficiency, recently. Individual's positive psychological capital can be developed in terms of high confidence (self-efficacy), optimism, hope, and resilience. Some empirical studies have attempted to define each of these four concepts as: Farmers' confidence and self-efficacy sometimes are interchangeably used to define farmer's beliefs about his/her abilities to achieve designated levels of performance (Judge et al., 2007 cited Bandura, 1994), or to take on and put in the necessary efforts to succeed at challenging farming tasks (Luthans et al., 2007). Optimism is another attribute of positive psychological capital, and mainly it is based on the expectancy oriented value model which speculates that, unless there is a valued goal, no action occurs (Carver et al., 2005). Therefore, optimistic behavior can be defined as individuals' future expectations or as a positive attribution about the present and future success (Carver et al., 2005; Luthans et al., 2007). For hope, it can be defined as individuals' perception of existing pathways, confidence and perseverance to achieve the desired performance (Luthans, Luthans, and Luthans, 2004; Carver et al., 2005; Luthans et al., 2007). Farmers' ability to maintain or to bounce back or a positive way of coping despite adversities/challenges defines another positive psychological capacity called resilience (Luthans, Luthans and Luthans, 2004; Ryan and Caltabiano, 2009). All the four defined

attributes of positive psychological capital can be of great relevance in enhancing the adoption of new technologies, increased agricultural productivity and flourishing smallholder farmers' agribusiness.

Despite its socio-economic importance, smallholder agriculture in the Eastern Cape Province has been reported as low-productive, stagnant, unsustainable and declining. The poor performance of this sector has resulted in widespread poverty, high unemployment, and high risks of food insecurity in the province. Having realized the poor performance, the South African government has devoted massive resources to stimulate agricultural growth as one sure way to eradicate poverty and improve food security among the rural-poor smallholders (ECDRDAR, 2011). Among strategies adopted included provision of farm support package includes subsidies on farm mechanization, irrigation systems, fertilizers, seeds, agro-chemicals, land rental costs and other necessary support (GoSA Information, 2008; Tregurtha, 2009). This support is thought to develop farmer's positive psychological capabilities. Smallholder farmers with high positive psychological capital (confidence, optimism, hope, and resilience) have a belief that they are more productive, recognized, motivated to invest in profitable technologies irrespective of risks and downfalls involved. When the farmer loses self-esteem that enables him/her to realize his/her confidence, optimism, hope and resilience, his positive psychological capacities deteriorates. Farmer's deteriorated positive psychological capacities are assumed to lead to low farm productivity, giving-up and resort entirely to hand-outs and social grants or opt for another profession (occupation).

Several studies related to farmer's low productivity, stagnant and being at the verge of giving-up suggest that loose farmer confidence, optimism, hope, and resilience because of farm related challenges. Perret (2004) and Manona *et al.* (2010) reported that smallholder irrigation plots in rural areas of South Africa are not intensively utilized and most of them are lying idle. Some of the challenges faced by smallholder farmers that are indirectly responsible for low positive psychological capital are: low farmer's interest and participation; lack of appropriate user-friendly irrigation infrastructural design; poor management and maintenance of irrigation facilities; Lack of necessary irrigation skills among beneficiaries and government extension officers; inadequate institutional structures; inadequate information about agricultural credit; lack of organized smallholder agricultural markets; low land productivity; high investment costs; and a history of dependency and subsistence orientation.

According to Roy (2009), some psychological factors resulting in loss of individual's confidence, optimism, hope, and resilience include a feeling of failure to achieve the desired results, suffering from helplessness, isolation, meaninglessness, and powerlessness. Due to loss of individual's positive psychological capital, the current study assumes that a farmer chooses to reduce investment or abandons his/her farm as a solution to challenges beyond his/her control. Several studies carried out by South African Water Research Commission (WRC) and agricultural economists have reported high rates of a declining number of farmers on small-scale irrigation schemes and some lie idle, and a large chunk of land abandoned by this category of farmers especially among rural-black people communities (Kibirige, 2013). However, these studies indicate that not all farmers facing these challenges abandon their fields and look for alternative sources of livelihood, but it is those who feel that they have exhausted all pathways of gaining access to government/private sector interventions that have opted out of farming. Abandonment of farms is an indication of loss of confidence, optimism, hope, and resilience. Precisely, farmer's positive psychological capacities related to declining smallholder-agricultural productivity in Eastern Cape Province have not been explored. Assuming abandonment of smallholder farms as the extreme stage of low positive psychological capital, the reasons of giving-up farming profession provide a basis of identifying the farm/farmer characteristics thought to be correlated with positive psychological capacities of smallholder farmers.

Doubtlessly, a vast body of literature attests that positive psychological capital contributes towards improved productivity and future anticipated returns (Luthans, Luthans and Luthans, 2004; Carver *et al.*, 2005; Judge *et al.*, 2007; Luthans *et al.*, 2007; Ryan and Caltabiano, 2009; Pepe *et al.*, 2010). Given a vast body of literature related to the association of positive psychological capital and individual's organization performance, little research if any has investigated the level and the determinants of smallholders farmers' positive psychological capital in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. This has resulted in a gap of knowledge for improved

delivery of psychological counseling among smallholder farmers in the Eastern Cape of South Africa. Therefore, this study aims at establishing the level of positive psychological capital and its determinants especially among smallholders whose livelihood is highly dependent on farming to contribute to the information key in grafting policies related to farmers' psychological counseling services.

2.1 Field Methods

This study was carried out in Cofimvaba-Qamata and Peddi-Ndlambe villages located in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. The study area was purposively selected because there are so many absentee farmers owning abandoned plots on small-scale irrigation schemes and those currently cultivating on these schemes their agricultural productivity are recorded low. Furthermore, farmers utilizing the schemes are still battling with high poverty level despite the availability of these key economically viable government smallholder support packages. This study used primary survey data collected by administering structured questions and physical observations. Farm/farmer characteristics related data was collected. Using a 4 point Likert scale, respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement in response to the 12 attitudinal statements, where "1" being strongly disagreed and "4" strongly agree. Some of the attitudinal statements used in this study were adapted from WIDCORP (2008), and Padilla-Fernandez and Nuthall (2001) and were redesigned to suit the research. Thirty eight and 41 respondents were interviewed by Qamata and Ndlambe villages, respectively resulting in a total of 79 interviewed smallholder farmers.

2.2 Analytical Methods

Factor analysis method was employed to generate the principal component of perceived farmers' positive psychological capacities (confidence, optimism, hope, and resilience). The purpose of using the factor analysis was to reduce a large number of variables (i.e., attitudinal statements) to a smaller set of new composite factors. This process also ensures a limited loss of information contained in a large number of attitudinal statements. The Eigenvalues greater than one, the Kaiser-Meyer-Oklin KMO score greater than 0.6 and Bartlett's test of sphericity was used to verify the suitability of data for Principal Component Analysis (WIDCORP, 2008; Kibirige, 2013). Following Kibirige (2013), the principal component (PC) of a given dataset of P numeric variables can be presented mathematically as:

$$PC_n = f(a_{n1}X_1, \dots, a_{nj}X_j) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where PC is the principal component, n represents a number greater than one. The PC can take different forms of measurement, and these include continuous variables, the quantity of related products of values that makeup a component, and weighted values or generated values from the component loading. The a_{1j} is the regression coefficient for the j^{th} variable and it is known as the eigenvector of the covariance matrix between variables. X_j is the value of the j^{th} variable. Explicitly the equation can be written as:

$$PC_1 = a_{11}X_1 + a_{12}X_2 + \dots \dots a_{1j}X_j \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where PC_1 = the first principal component. X_1 and X_2 are the first and second independent variables of PC_1 in the linear additive model needed to derive the principal component, and the a_{11} and a_{12} are coefficient (component loadings) associated with the X_1 and X_2 variables.

2.2.1 Positive psychological capital and Farmer/Farm Characteristics

The impact of socioeconomic characteristics on farmer's positive psychological capacities was estimated using factor analysis and multivariate regression analysis. The multivariate regression analysis used standard factor scores generated after the factor analysis was performed, and these scores were regressed on farm/farmers' socioeconomic characteristics. Thus:

$$FS_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1SEX + \beta_2AGE + \beta_3EDUC + \beta_4EXPE + \beta_5LANDSIZE + \beta_6GOVS + \beta_7TRAINING + \beta_8SOURCWAT + \beta_8SOURCLAB + \beta_9COOP + \beta_{10}RMSGP + \beta_{11}EXTENS + \beta_{12}CREDIT + \beta_{13}HHSIZE + e \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where FSij (dependent variable) = generated regression factor analysis scores, β = coefficient parameters to be measured, e = error term, explanatory variable include SEX = sex of respondent (1 =male, 2= female), AGE = age of the farmer (years), EDUC = education level of the farmer (years), EXPE = farming experience (years) of the farmer, LANDSIZE = size of land owned (hectares), GOVS =whether farmer receive government support (1 = yes and 2 = No) , TRAINING = number of trainings received by the farmer in one season, SOURCWAT = Source of water for crop production (Rain, tap, dam, river, or spring), SOURCLAB = source of farm labor (1 =family , 2= hired labor), COOP = whether farmer belongs to a cooperative (1 = yes, 2= No), RMSGP = remittances, social grants and pension amount received by the farm household (Rand), EXTENS = whether farmer receives extension services (1 = yes, 2 = No), CREDIT = whether farmer accesses credit/loan services (1 = yes, 2 = No) and HHSIZE = household size or number of family members in the respondent’s household.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Farmers and Farm Characteristics

Farmers’ demographic and farm related data is presented in Table 1. Data presented in Table 1 were categorized into two, the non-continuous and continuous variables. The non-continuous variables are sex of respondent, the source of farm labor, the source of water for farming, membership to cooperatives, farmers’ access to government support, access to extension services and access to credit/loan services.

Table 1a: Social Demographic Characteristics of Sampled Farmers (n=79)

Item	Description	Frequency	Percentage	Standard Deviation
Sex of respondent	Male	44.0	56	0.500
	Female	35.0	44	
Sources of farm labor	Family	62.0	78	0.717
	Hired	06.0	8	
	Both	11.0	14	
Source of water used in farming	River	40.0	51	1.767
	Rainwater	23.0	29	
	Dams	12.0	16	
	Piped water	04.0	4	
Belong to farmer cooperative	Yes	41.0	52	0.503
	No	38.0	48	
Government support (farm-inputs)	Yes	15	19	0.395
	No	64	81	
Access extension services	Yes	39.5	50	0.503
	No	39.5	50	
Access to credit	Yes	08.0	10	0.304
	No	71.0	90	

Table 1b: Social Demographic Characteristics of Sampled Farmers (n=79)

Continuous Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Age of household head	30.00	79.00	58.22	12.725
Household size of respondent	1.00	14.00	4.72	2.913
Years spent in the School of respondent	0.00	16.00	5.48	4.711
Years spent in farming of respondent	0.00	50.00	10.29	12.791
Amount of land owned	0.25	6.00	1.03	1.181
Number of times received training	0.00	30.00	3.79	7.133
Remittances	0.00	22400.00	3645.19	4319.825

Source: Results from SPSS (version 11) generated from Field Survey, 2012.

Generated results in Table 1 indicate that there were slightly more men (56%) involved in farming than women in the study area. The findings further indicate that 78% of farmers depend on family farm labour, and 51% of farmers majorly rely on irrigation-water drawn from rivers. At least 52% of interviewed farmers indicated that

they belonged to a farmer cooperative, and only 19% of sampled farmers had access to government support in terms of farm input-subsidies. Results further indicate that there are relatively fewer farmers (10%) accessing agricultural credit and 50% of sampled farmers had access to extension services.

Continuous variables presented in Table 1 constitute age of farmer, a household size of a farmer, years spent in school, years spent in farming, amount of land owned, number of times received training in a season, and remittances (social grants, pension, other incomes received as gifts). Farmers were aged (Mean = 58.22, SD=12.73 years) and their family size was comparatively middle sized (mean \approx 5, SD = 2.91 family members). Farmers exhibited low education level (mean years attending formal education = 5.48, SD = 4.71) and had a relatively longer experience in farming (Mean years of experience = 10.29, SD=12.79). Their irrigated-farm plots were very small (Mean = 1.03, SD=1.18 hectares). Although farmers received relatively few frequencies of training in a season (Mean = 3.79, SD=7.13), they were receiving reasonable amounts of social grants from the government as a secondary source of livelihood (Mean = 3645.19, SD = 4319.82 Rand/season). These social grants were mainly given to helpless children, and each child was receiving at least R280 while elderly and pensioners were receiving at least R1200 per month.

The Principal Components for the Perceived Positive Psychological Capital

Using collected data on the 12-attitudinal/behavioral statements related to positive psychological, factor analysis was performed. Factor loadings method was employed to elicit factors that explain the variances statistically within the statements, and the farmer's perceived positive psychological capital principal components were generated. Four farmers' perceived principal components were extracted, and they explained 67.69% variance in responses. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy (0.657) was above the recommended minimum score value of 0.60. The Bartlett's test of Sphericity test also indicated the worthiness of the analysis. Based on the factor correlation with positive psychological capital behavioural statements, the extracted three principal components can be best described as hope, resilience, optimism, and confidence.

The most correlated positive psychological capital related statements that best described the first principal component were mainly related to hope. This principal component was explained by 24.73% of the variance in the explanatory variables with four estimated coefficients above 0.3 being positive. Farmers' perceived hope related variables with coefficients above 0.3 were: be recognized as a leader in the technology adoption, be recognized as a top producer, be recognized as a specialist in growing a given crop, and irrespective of challenges, the farmer continues to try till the solution is got. Highly hopeful farmers had less consideration of being self-employed and independent, expanding their businesses, and supplying produce on credit as these statements exhibited negative coefficients. The second extracted principal component can be best defined as a farmer's resilience. This principal component was explained by 23.01% of the explanatory variables with eight estimated coefficients above 0.3, and all had positive coefficients. The eight behavioral statements that described the farmer's perceived resilience included being self-employed and independent; expand business; having the ability to organize available resources to achieve a goal; willingness to source for information at all costs; do not wait for subsidies before applying new technology; risks of adopting new technologies not considered as a first priority when taking decisions; irrespective of challenges, the farmer continues to try until the solution is got; and the farmer can supply produce on credit.

Table 3: The Principal Components of Perceived Farmers' Positive Psychological Capital

	Principal Components			
	1	2	3	4
<i>Eigen Value</i>	2.967	2.761	1.332	1.062
<i>Proportional of Variation</i>	24.727	23.011	11.099	8.851
	Hope	Resilience	Optimistic	Confidence
Being self-employed and independent	<u>-0.524</u>	<u>0.492</u>	<u>-0.314</u>	0.243
Be recognized as a leader in the technology adoption	<u>0.890</u>	-0.008	-0.077	0.078
Be recognized as top producer	<u>0.876</u>	0.008	-0.127	0.165
Be recognized as a specialist in growing these crop	<u>0.619</u>	0.274	-0.009	<u>0.538</u>
Expand the business	<u>-0.474</u>	<u>0.446</u>	0.149	<u>0.441</u>
You have the ability to organize available resources to achieve a goal	0.198	<u>0.652</u>	-0.289	0.074
Take action always on the basis of what you perceive profitable	0.111	-0.280	<u>0.676</u>	<u>0.475</u>
Do not wait for subsidies before applying new technology	0.145	<u>0.527</u>	<u>0.454</u>	<u>-0.329</u>
Willing to source for information at all costs	0.283	<u>0.541</u>	<u>0.333</u>	-0.251
Risks of new technologies isn't your first priority to take a decision	-0.146	<u>0.763</u>	<u>0.438</u>	-0.062
Irrespective of challenges I continue trying till the solution is got.	<u>0.483</u>	<u>0.553</u>	-0.246	-0.218
Can supply produce on credit	<u>-0.343</u>	<u>0.532</u>	-0.280	0.182

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy = 0.657

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: Approx. Chi-Square = 328.052

Degree of freedom = 66

Model significance level = 1%

Source: Results from SPSS (Version 11) generated from field survey, 2012. Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. The bold and underlined factors > (0.3) qualify to constitute a given Principal component.

The third principal component generated was explained by 11.10% of the explanatory variables and can be best described as optimism. Results displayed in Table 3 suggest that farmers with higher optimistic behavior indicated that they would take action always on the basis of what they perceive profitable, do not wait for subsidies before applying new technology, they are willing to source for information at all costs, and risks associated with the adoption of new technologies were not their first priority when taking a decision. However, farmers with higher optimistic behavior do not consider self-employed and independent as a driving factor of optimism because this factor possessed a negative coefficient. Farmers' confidence behavior was best described by the fourth principal component. The extracted fourth principal component was explained by 8.85% of the explanatory variables. According to results shown in Table 3, highly confident farmers are more likely to be interested in being recognized as a specialist in growing crops of interest, more likely to expand their business, and take action always on the basis of what he/she perceives to be profitable. Nevertheless, Table 3 shows that farmers with high confidence level were more likely to wait for subsidies before applying new technologies as this statement exhibited a negative coefficient.

The relationship between Perceived Positive Psychological Capital and Farm/Farmer Characteristics

Using multiple regression analysis models, the association between the farm/farmer characteristics and farmers' goals were established. Results indicate a significant relationship between the farm/farmer characteristics and farmer's goals as presented in Table 4. The four regression models related to farmers' perceived hope, resilience, optimistic, and confidence are all significant at 1% level, respectively. Based on results presented in Table 4, farmers' hope in small-scale farming is positively and significantly dependent on the size of land owned at 10% level, access to government support, and dependence on farm family labour both at 1% significant level, respectively. Thus, farmers with larger pieces of land, who have access to government support in terms of input-subsidies, and are dependent on cheap family labour are more likely to have higher hope than their counterparts. Elderly farmers who have spent many years in farming and had access to extension services are more likely to have low levels of hope since results indicate a negative and significant impact of age, years of farming and access to extension services. Generally, since the average age of farmers (58 years) is above the youthful farm productive age as indicated by Ongundele and Okoruwa (2006), and it should be noted that farmers in this study area possess low levels of hope.

According to findings presented in Table 4, age of the farmer, household size, years spent in school, years spent farming, source of water, remittances (child grants, elderly pension, and gifts in the form of cash), and access to credit/loan had a high positive and significant impact on farmers' perceived resiliency behavior. With the

exception of remittances which was significant at 10% level, all other positively related factors perceived as farmer's resiliency behavior were significant at 1% level, respectively. This is an indication that highly resilient farmers in the study area can be described as those who are aged with larger family size, attained higher formal education, more farming experience, extracting farm water from the river, have more access to social grants, and more access to credit/loans. Farm/farmer characteristics found to have a negative and significant impact on farmers' perceived resilience are a source of farm labour, and access to extension services at 1% and 10% level, respectively. Thus, farmers' dependency on cheap family labour and access to extension services weakens their resiliency. Since family members in most cases may have different responsibilities, they may not be a reliable source of labour, and sometimes extension workers may give advice hard to implement, thus, restraining farmer's enthusiasm and resilience.

Table 4: Relationship between Positive Psychological Capital and Farm/Farmer Characteristics

	Hope		Resilience		Optimistic		Confidence	
	B	P-Value	B	P-Value	B	P-Value	B	P-Value
Gender of farmer	0.248	0.696	0.318	0.515	-2.459	0.032**	1.779	0.006***
Age of the farmer	-0.052	0.001***	0.063	0.000***	0.038	0.126	0.017	0.212
Household size	0.007	0.926	0.404	0.000***	-0.387	0.005***	0.284	0.000***
Years spent in school	0.025	0.555	0.185	0.000***	-0.240	0.002***	0.262	0.000***
Years Farming	-0.046	0.000***	0.054	0.000***	-0.048	0.010***	0.010	0.326
Size of land owned	0.355	0.083*	0.224	0.149	-0.301	0.381	-0.264	0.166
Source of water	-0.053	0.777	0.664	0.000***	-0.854	0.013***	0.458	0.014***
Source of farm labour	0.837	0.003***	-0.707	0.001***	-0.917	0.044**	0.086	0.718
Government support	2.122	0.000***	-0.207	0.520	-0.775	0.288	1.675	0.000***
membership to cooperative	0.348	0.686	0.174	0.791	-1.561	0.296	1.705	0.044**
Remittances	0.000	0.698	0.000	0.055*	-0.000	0.007**	0.000	0.004***
Access to credit/loan	-0.081	0.867	1.294	0.002***	0.849	0.313	2.176	0.000***
Number of trainings	-0.000	0.999	-0.034	0.292	0.170	0.024**	-0.074	0.068*
Access extension services	-0.788	0.065*	-0.537	0.097*	2.725	0.001**	-0.541	0.170
(Constant)	-1.386	0.618	-10.410	0.000***	8.804	0.074*	-16.245	0.000***
R-squared adjusted	0.855		0.904		0.529		0.866	
F-value	16.638***		25.937***		3.964***		18.057***	

Source: Results from SPSS (Version 11) generated from field survey, 2012. Where ****, **, * = significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively: β = coefficients and p-value = probability value.

Optimistic farmers are more likely to have attended more training and have more access to extension services since results displayed in Table 4 indicate a positive and significant relationship between optimism, and number of trainings and access to extension services, both at 5% level, respectively. Sex of respondent and source of farm labour had a negative and significant impact on farmers' optimistic behavior at 5% level, respectively, while household size, years spent in school, farming experience, source of farm-water, and remittances were negatively and significantly associated with perceived farmers' optimistic behavior at 1% level, respectively. Farmers with low optimistic behavior are more likely to be men with relatively large household size, spent more years in school and have more farming experience, draw water from the river, depending on farm family labour, and highly depend on social grants.

The findings of this study indicated a positive and significant relationship between perceived farmers' confidence, and farm/farmer characteristics like sex of respondent, household size, years spent in school, government support, source of water, remittances, and access to credit/loan at 1% level, respectively, and membership to cooperative at 5% level. A number of training had a negative and significant relationship with perceived farmers' confidence at a 10% level. This is an indication that farmers with high confidence are more likely to be men, having relatively more family members, spent more years in school, receives more government support, use irrigation water from the river, receives more social grants, have more access to credits/loan, and are members in cooperatives. Further, this is an indication that education, input-subsidies, water availability, financial and social capital are key in instill farmers' confidence.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Results noted high optimistic and confidence levels with low hope and resilience levels among sampled farmers. Thus, although farmers can easily invest in new opportunities and have the self-efficacy, they can

hardly find solutions to farm challenges and anticipated risks. The key farm/farmer characteristics responsible for high optimism behavior among farmers are a number of training and access to extension service. For farmer's confidence behaviors, results indicate that it is mainly influenced by the sex of respondent, household size, years spent in school, government support, and source of water, remittances and access to credit/loan, respectively. However, stimulation or consideration of a single positive psychological attribute may not yield meaningful results. Therefore, more than one of the four positive psychological attributes may be desired to cause a significant impact. Based on the findings, the crucial farm/farmer characteristics that have a positive and significant influence on at least more than one positive psychological attribute included education, the source of water, access to credit, and household size for resilience and confidence. Government support in the form of input-subsidies positively and significantly affects both hope and confidence level of farmers.

Since farmers' positive psychological capital as defined in this study are not things that are amenable to direct policy intervention, they can only be modified indirectly through policy actions that affect their determinants. This study recommends that government, NGOs/CBOs, private companies, and other development partners should focus/catalyze improved farmers' positive psychological capacities for increased farmers' productivity and reduced poverty levels through:

- 1) Improved access to formal education that enables farmers' reading and interpretation of information related to adoption and use of high yielding technologies.
- 2) We are ensuring farmers' access to water for irrigation in a less costly manner like the establishment of smallholder irrigation schemes near natural water bodies including rivers and springs.
- 3) Improved farmers' access to agro-finance facilities or ensure banks and micro-finance institutions get closer to smallholder farmers in rural areas. Further, revise the interest rates to suit resource-poor farmers' abilities. Farmers' should be encouraged to form village savings and credit cooperatives.
- 4) Farmers' increased access to government input-subsidies especially for the resource-poor who can hardly raise start-up capital should be considered.

References:

- i. Carver, C. S., R. G Smith, M. H. Antoni, V. M. Petronis, S. Weiss, & R.P. Derhagopian, 2005, "Optimistic personality and psychosocial well-being during treatment predict psychosocial well-being among long-term survivors of breast cancer", *Health Psychology*, 24, 508-516.
- ii. Roy D.D., 2009 "Self-Efficacy of Agricultural Farmers: A Case Study" *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology* July 2009, Vol. 35, No. 2, 323-293: Indian Statistical Institute, Kolkata
- iii. Eastern Cape Province Department of Rural Development and Agrarian Reform (ECDRDAR), 2011, *Strategic Plan 2010/11-2014/15 (updated 2011/12); "Towards Vibrant, Equitable and Sustainable Rural Communities and Food Security"*.
- iv. South African Government Information, 2008, "Programmes in the Eastern Cape", www.info.gov.za/issues/govtprog/ecape.htm: 27th August 2008.
- v. Judge TA., C L. Jackson, JC. Shaw, BA. Scott and BL. Rich, 2007. "Self-Efficacy and Work-Related Performance: The Integral Role of Individual Differences", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 2007, Vol. 92, No. 1, 107-127.
- vi. Kibirige D., 2013 "The Impact of Human Dimensions on Smallholder Farming in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa" PhD Thesis, Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension Faculty of Science and Agriculture University of Fort Hare, Alice, South Africa
- vii. Luthans F., K.W. Luthans, and B.C. Luthans, 2004, "Positive psychological capital: Beyond human and social capital", *Business Horizons* 47/1 January-February 2004 (45-50).
- viii. Luthans, F., B.J. Avolio, J.B. Avey, and S.M., Norman, 2007, "Positive psychological capital: measurement and relationship with performance and satisfaction", *Leadership Institute Faculty Publications, Paper 11*.
- ix. Machethe, C. L., K. Mollel, K. Ayisi, M. B. Mashatola, F. D. K. Anim and F. Vanaxhe, 2004. *Smallholder irrigation and agricultural development in the Olifants River Basin of Limpopo Province:*

- Management transfer, productivity, profitability and food security issues, WRC Report No 1050/1/04. Pretoria: Water Research Commission.*
- x. *Manona S., J. Denison, W. Van Averbeke and T. Masiya, 2010, —Proposed Land Tenure and Land Administration Interventions to Increase Productivity on Smallholder Irrigation Schemes in South Africa”, Paper presented at the conference on Overcoming inequality and structural poverty in South Africa: towards inclusive growth and development, PLAAS, SPII and Isandla Institute, Johannesburg.*
- xi. *Ogundele O. O and O. V. Okoruwa, 2006, “Techical Efficiency Differential in Rice Production Technologies in Nigeria”, Africa Research Consortium, Research paper 154.*
- xii. *Padilla-Fernandez M. D. and P. Nuthall, 2001, Farmers” goals and efficiency in the production of sugar cane: The Philippine case, Farm and Horticultural Management Group Lincoln University, ISSN 1174-8796, Research Report 07/2001.*
- xiii. *Pepe SJ., M.L Farnese, F. Avalone, and M. Vecchione, 2010, “Work self-efficacy scale and search for work self-efficacy scale: A validation study in Spanish and Italian cultural contexts”, ISSN: 1576-5962 - DOI: 10.5093/tr2010v26n3a4.*
- xiv. *Perret S. R., 2004, “Local empowerment in smallholder irrigation schemes: A methodology for participatory diagnosis and prospective analysis”. University of Pretoria & CIRAD, Department of Agricultural Economics, Extension and Rural Development, Pretoria, South Africa.*
- xv. *Ryan L. and M L. Caltabiano, 2009, “Development of a New Resilience Scale: The Resilience in Midlife Scale (RIM Scale)”, Asian Social Science Journal-vol. 5, No.11, November 2009, Department of Psychology, James Cook University, Australia.*
- xvi. *Steyn G.J., 1982, “Livestock production in the Amatola Basin”, Master’s Thesis, University of Fort Hare, Alice, South Africa.*
- xvii. *Tregurtha N., 2009, “Review of the Eastern Cape’s Siyakhula/Massive maize project”, Trade and Industrial Policy Strategies.*
- xviii. *Water in Dry-land Collaborative Research Program (WIDCORP), 2008, “Identifying farmer typologies, attitudes and aspirations of the WimmeraMallee Pipeline – Supply System 6”. A report prepared for the Department of Primary Industries, Horsham, December 2008, Report no. 3/08.*